

First person imperative in Dolgan – Clusivity or number distinction?¹

Chris Lasse Däbritz (Hamburg)

Abstract

The study at hand investigates the first person imperative forms of Dolgan (< North-Siberian Turkic < Turkic). Although Dolgan exhibits only two numbers (singular and plural), there are three forms in the first person imperative, whence the question arises in which functional domains these forms do occur. After some theoretical preliminaries are dealt with (section 2), three analyses of the forms are discussed (section 3.1): 1. number distinction (cf. Korkina 1970), 2. clusivity distinction inclusive vs. exclusive (cf. Ubrjatova 1985, Artem'ev 2013b) and 3. clusivity distinction minimal inclusive vs. augmented inclusive (cf. Dobrushina & Goussev 2005, Nevskaja 2005). Finally, it is argued (section 3.2) that the forms can indeed be described most appropriately via a number distinction, whereby in many cases this correlates to a clusivity distinction minimal inclusive vs. augmented inclusive.

Keywords: Dolgan, North-Siberian Turkic, languages of the Taymyr peninsula, imperative, clusivity, dual

1. Introduction

Dolgan is a Turkic language (North-Siberian Turkic < Siberian Turkic), spoken by approx. 1,000 people (VPN 2010) on the Taymyr peninsula in the extreme north of the Russian Federation. Though being closely related to Yakut (Sakha) from a structural point of view, nowadays, there is high agreement that Dolgan is to be considered a language of its own and not a dialect of Yakut (Artem'ev 2013a: 27, Ubrjatova 1985: 3f.). Being spoken on the Taymyr peninsula and in adjacent areas, Dolgan is in contact with the neighboring languages Nganasan, Tundra Nenets and Forest Enets (all < Samoyedic < Uralic) in the west, with Evenki (< Tungusic) in the south and with Yakut (< Turkic) in the east. Moreover, in all official spheres of life Russian is the dominant language. Nevertheless, there are three settlements (Novorybnoe, Syndassko and Popigay, each located

¹ This publication has been produced in the context of the joint research funding of the German Federal Government and Federal States in the Academies' Programme, with funding from the Federal Ministry of Education and Research and the Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg. The Academies' Programme is coordinated by the Union of the German Academies of Sciences and Humanities.

east of the Khatanga river and Khatanga bay), where Dolgan is still spoken in everyday's life by the majority of inhabitants (cf. Stapert 2013: 17ff.).

Dolgan can be regarded as a typical Turkic language with respect to its grammatical system: It exhibits vowel harmony, rich agglutinative nominal and verbal morphology, its syntax is mostly head-final. In verbal morphology, the categories of tense and aspect are closely intertwined, furthermore, there are a handful to a dozen of modal forms, including the imperative. In verbal paradigms, Dolgan distinguishes three persons and two numbers, cf. the following present tense paradigm of the verb *bar-* 'to go'²:

	SG	PL
1	<i>bar-a-bin</i>	<i>bar-a-bit</i>
2	<i>bar-a-gin</i>	<i>bar-a-git</i>
3	<i>bar-ar</i>	<i>bar-al-lar</i>

Tab. 1: Present tense forms of *bar-* 'to go'

In the imperative, however, there are three forms distinguished in the first person, which cannot be discriminated against each other merely by the category of number, cf. the following imperative paradigm of the verb *bar-* 'to go':

	SG	PL
1	<i>bar-i:m ~ bar-iāk ~ bar-iāgiŋ</i>	
2	<i>bar</i>	<i>bar-iŋ</i>
3	<i>bar-din</i>	<i>bar-dinnar</i>

Tab. 2: Imperative forms of *bar-* 'to go'

The corresponding deep forms of the person-number suffixes are as follows:

	SG	PL
1	-I:m ~ -IAk ~ -IAgIŋ	
2	-Ø	-iŋ
3	-DIIn	-DIInAr

Tab. 3: Personal endings in the imperative

As can be seen from the tables, there is neither a clearly distinguishable imperative morpheme nor a consistent way of building the forms. In the 2nd person singular, there is no ending, i.e., the form is homonymous to the stem of the

² *-a-* in the first and second person as well as *-ar-* (and *-al-* resp.) in the third person are present tense markers grammaticalized from non-finite verb forms. The personal endings come from the "predicative row", they are, hence, functional equivalents to Turkish *-(y)Im, -sIn* etc.

verb, which is the typical pattern in the Turkic languages (Johanson 1998: 44). In the 2nd person plural, the ending is *-ŋ*, which is added to the verbal stem. In the 3rd person singular, the suffix *-DIn* is attached to the verbal stem; in the 3rd person plural, this suffix is extended with the plural marker *-LAr*. The first suffix in the first person *-I:m* is attached to the verbal stem, as well as the second suffix *-IAk*. The third suffix, finally, *-IAgIŋ* is a combination of the suffix *-IAk* and the suffix of the 2nd person plural *-ŋ* (cf. Nevskaja 2005: 348).

Whereas the functional domains of the second and third person forms are clear, this does not hold true for the first person forms. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to shed light on the nature of the functional distinction of the imperative forms in the first person in Dolgan. Both a clusivity (inclusive vs. exclusive as well as minimal vs. augmented inclusive) and a number distinction have been proposed earlier, hence, the question arises which analysis is right or whether rather a combination of them is most appropriate. The analysis in this paper bases on the INEL Dolgan corpus (Däbritz et al. 2019), which contains mostly spontaneous speech of Dolgan as well as some written folklore texts. The corpus consists of 116 transcripts with 11,329 utterances and 77,636 tokens.

The paper is organized as follows: In section 2, some theoretical background is provided. In section 3.1, prior accounts to the problem are presented and in section 3.2, the corpus data at hand is analyzed. Section 4 draws a conclusion and evaluates the outcomes against a broader background. Finally, I would like to thank Alexandre Arkhipov and Beáta Wagner-Nagy for their valuable comments on an earlier draft of this paper; it goes without saying that I alone am responsible for all remaining mistakes and obscurities.

2. Theoretical preliminaries

As the following analysis is partly very fine-grained, some theoretical comments and terminological clarifications are in order here. First of all, the term *imperative* has to be clarified. Imperatives are linguistic expressions of directive illocutionary acts (cf. Searle 1975: 355), hence, they express a request or an order (Gusev 2013: 11). As this request or order is most often placed by the speaker and addressed to the hearer(s), the dominant domain of imperatives is the second person (ibid.). Whether or not other persons can be the addressee of imperatives – or, more precisely, the potential executor of the action – is a matter of discussion. Here I follow the approach of i.a. Gusev (2013: 28f.) that all persons can be the addressee of imperatives, hence, also the named first person forms in Dolgan can be regarded as imperative forms. Terms like *optative*, *hortative* or *adhortative* (first person) or *jussive* (third person) are not used here.

The term *number* refers to that grammatical category which expresses the amount of referents referred to. Singular expressions refer to one referent, dual

expressions refer to exactly two referents and plural expressions refer to many referents. Hence, if a language exhibits a dual, then two referents are referred to with the dual, if it does not exhibit a dual, then two referents are referred to with the plural.

Finally, the terms *inclusive* and *exclusive* have to be clarified. *Inclusive* means that both the speaker and the addressee(s) is/are included in a set of referents in a given context, *exclusive* means that the addressee(s) is/are excluded from this set (Filimonova 2005: ix). The most prototypical expression of this distinction is the presence of more than one first person non-singular pronoun in a language, cf. e.g. Evenki *bu*: ‘we (excluding the hearer)’ vs. *mit* ‘we (including the hearer)’ (Bulatova & Grenoble 1999: 21).

3. First-person imperative in Dolgan

3.1. Prior accounts

The first systematic attempt to explain the existence of three first person imperative forms in North Siberian Turkic languages was made by Evdokija Korkina (1970), analyzing the mood system of Yakut. For Yakut, Korkina (1970: 147f.) states explicitly that there are three numbers in the first person of the imperative (singular, dual, plural), whereby -I:m would express singular, -IAχ would express dual and -IAγIη³ would express plural. The status of -I:m is undisputed in all following approaches, being considered as the imperative of the first person singular, which is used exclusively in singular contexts (Artem’ev 2013: 207, Ubrjatova 1985: 178, Li 2011: 146). Therefore, this form will not be discussed further here.

As for the forms -IAk and -IAgIη, there are more controversial approaches. Ubrjatova (1985: 179ff.) describes the forms as exclusive (I and you.SG) and inclusive (I and you.SG and you.PL) respectively; moreover, she labels Korkina’s dual interpretation (see above) as “widespread misbelief among turcologists”. Li (2011: 146) follows Ubrjatova’s analysis. Artem’ev (2013b: 207) states that the form -IAk refers to exactly two subjects and is, hence, often regarded as dual. Nevertheless, according to him the form is to be regarded as plural exclusive (opposed to the plural inclusive -IAgIη), because both forms would express plural semantics (ibid.). It is important to note here that all authors seem to understand the distinction *inclusive* vs. *exclusive* as including a third person or not instead of including the addressee(s) or not. Hence, both number and clusivity somehow play a role in the first person non-singular imperative in Dolgan according to existing grammatical descriptions. Not regarding the diverse denominations of the phenomenon, one can carefully draw the conclusion that there is agreement that the form -IAk refers to speaker and addressee

3 -IAχ are -IAγIη are the Yakut cognates of Dolgan -IAk and -IAgIη, respectively.

(I and you.SG), whilst the form -IAGIŋ refers to speaker, addressee(s) and other people (I and you.SG/PL and others).

Nevskaja (2005: 343) as well as Dobrushina & Goussev (2005: 206) analyze the Dolgan and Yakut forms as the opposition of minimal vs. augmented inclusive imperative. *Minimal inclusive imperatives* refer to the speaker and the addressee, hence to two persons, whereas *augmented inclusive imperatives* refer to the speaker, one or more addressee(s) and/or persons not present in the speech situation, hence, to more than two persons (Dobrushina & Goussev 2005: 202). This is also why the opposition of minimal vs. augmented inclusive is often considered to be a pure number distinction dual vs. plural (ibid.). The most important point is, hence, that neither of the authors agrees with the grammatical descriptions of Dolgan (and Yakut) in that -IAk and -IAGIŋ (or -IAχ and -IAγIŋ resp.) would express the opposition exclusive vs. inclusive. Instead, they analyze it as the opposition minimal inclusive vs. augmented inclusive, which due to the typical constellation of the speech situation implies a number opposition dual vs. plural.

Thus, there is no agreement at all in what terms and categories the first person imperative forms -IAk and -IAGIŋ in Dolgan can be described. In the next section, these forms and their functions will be analyzed on the base of the INEL Dolgan corpus.

3.2. Corpus-based analysis

In the analyzed corpus data, 84 instances of first person non-singular imperatives were found. Out of them, 57 forms are built with the suffix -IAk and 27 forms are built with the suffix -IAGIŋ. The following four examples show typical occurrences of them⁴:

- (1) *Bi:rdε kutujak taba-ni kör-ön*
 once mouse reindeer-ACC see-CVB.SEQ
d̄ie-bit: “Taba, kisten-el-e
 say-PST2.3SG reindeer hide-FRQ-CVB.SIM
o:nn’-uok!”
play-IMP.1NSG
 ‘Once the mouse saw the reindeer and said: “Reindeer, let’s play hide and seek!”’
 (AkEE_19900810_ReindeerMouse_flk.002-003)

⁴ In order to not presuppose any interpretation of the forms in advance, both forms are glossed as IMP.1NSG within this paper.

- (2) “*Be:be,* *iti* *tur-ar* *tüs-tün,*
 wait that stand-PTCP.PRS fall-IMP.3SG
kör-üök *bu-lar-i,* [...]”
see-IMP.1NSG this-PL-ACC
 ‘Wait, may it be like that, let’s look at these, [...]’
 (ChGS_UoPP_20170724_SocCogOrder_conv.ChGS.010)
- (3) *Bi:rde* *araj* *ira:kta:gi* *uol-a*
 once just czar son-POSS3SG
dīe-bit: “*Dogot-tor,* *ti:-lan-a*
 say-PST2.3SG friend-PL small.boat-VBZ-CVB.SIM
bar-īagij!”
go-IMP.1NSG
 ‘Once the czar’s son said: “Friends, let’s have a boat ride!”’
 (ChPK_1970_ThreeBoys_flk.034-035)
- (4) *Kuōka: hūbehit-e:* “*Ani* *heri:leh-en* ***büt-üögüy!***”
 pike leader-POSS3SG now fight-CVB.SEQ **stop-IMP.1NSG**
 ‘The pikes’ leader: “Let’s stop fighting now!”’
 (ErSV_1964_WarPartridgesPikes_flk.057-058)

Already from these examples it becomes clear that the forms built with -IAk and -IAgIḡ respectively do not express aclusivity distinction in the simplest sense, as in (1)–(2) as well as in (3)–(4) the addressee is included in the set of referents. The difference between (1)–(2) and (3)–(4), apparently, is the number of referents included. In (1), e.g., the mouse (speaker) and the reindeer (addressee) form a pair, whereas in (3), e.g., the czar’s son (speaker) and his friends (addressees) form a group of three. As the other instances in the corpus behave likewise, aclusivity opposition *exclusive* vs. *inclusive* of the suffixes -IAk and -IAgIḡ can be excluded for Dolgan. Thus, there remain the possibilities of aclusivity opposition *minimal inclusive* vs. *augmented inclusive* and a number opposition *dual* vs. *plural*. These oppositions, however, are difficult to distinguish within the category of imperative, as the imperative by its nature is prototypically already inclusive (Gusev 2013: 46, 203). Exclusive contexts of first person imperatives are hard to find, but nonetheless can be found, cf. the following German phraseologized example:

- (5) *Seien* *wir* *nicht* *so,* *hier* *hast*
 be.CONJ.1PL we not so here have.2SG
du *auch* *ein* *Stück* *Kuchen.*
 you also a piece cake
 ?‘Don’t let us be so [mean], here is a piece of cake for you, too.’

The conjunctive form *seien* is used as a first person imperative marker here. The exact meaning of the phrase *seien wir nicht so* is hard to convey, in any case not the addressee but the speaker and “his/her” people are asked here not to be so mean. This means that the addressee is excluded from the set of referents here, though the second clause makes clear that s/he indeed is the person talked to. Interestingly, there are languages where these contexts can be expressed morphologically, e.g. South Siberian Turkic languages. The following Khakas examples illustrate this:

- (6) a. *Abakanan-zar* *par* *kil-eler.*
 Abakan-ALL go come-IMP.1PL.INCL
 ‘Let’s (I and you many) go to Abakan.’
 (Dobrushina & Goussev 2005: 195)
- b. *Pis* *par* *kil-ips* *Abakan-zar;*
 1PL go come-IMP.1PL.EXCL Abakan-ALL,
a *sin* *minda* *xal* *tur.*
 and 2SG here stay stand.IMP.2SG
 ‘We (I and some other people) go to Abakan, and you stay here.’
 (Dobrushina & Goussev 2005: 195)

In (6)a the addressee is included in the set of persons who will go to Abakan, in (6)b not. Hence, in (6)a an inclusive form is used, in (6)b an exclusive form. Dolgan does not exhibit special exclusive forms. Hence, the question arises whether the forms -IAk and -IAgIŋ can be used in contexts like (6)b or not. If this is the case, then it can be said that the forms are not pure inclusives as e.g. Nevskaja (2005) considered them to be (see above).

In most examples with both forms the addressee(s) is/are indeed included in the set of referents, which is not surprising as this is the prototypical context of an imperative. However, there are few examples where this reading can be excluded, cf. example (7) for the form -IAk:

- (7) Context: Two girls are going for water. One of them stumbles over the legs of the main protagonist. They start talking, it becomes clear that the girl's father made a riddle. Who solves the riddle, can marry the girl. Now the girl tells the protagonist what is the solution for the riddle.

Iti-ni gin-ar e-bit-e du;
 that-ACC make-PTCP.PRS be-PST2-3SG MOD

če, bar-îak!
 well go-IMP.1NSG

'That is apparently what he means, well, let's go!'

(BeVP_1970_Laajku_flk.059-060)

From the following context it becomes clear that not the protagonist and the girl are going away, but the girl and her friend. This means that not the addressee of the utterance in (7) is included into the set of referents, but a third person. Hence, the reading of the imperative form is exclusive here. For the form -IAgIŋ, a similar example could be found:

- (8) Context: People are fishing with a seine. One man, Nojoon, is standing at the shore and holding one end of the seine. The other people are in a boat and are pulling the seine, in order to surround a school of fish. Now one of the people in the boat is waving to Nojoon and shouting something.

Ist-i-bit, dogor-o d-i:r:
 hear-EP-PST2.3SG friend-POSS3SG say-PRS.3SG

“Türgen-nik ka:m-îagiŋ tard-a
 quick-ADV go-IMP.1NSG pull-CVB.SIM

tüh-e-tüh-e!”
 fall-CVB.SIM-fall-CVB.SIM

'He [= Nojoon] heard [that] his friend says: “Let's go quickly in order to pull!”'

(PoNA_19910207_Fishing_nar.184)

Here, only an exclusive reading makes factually sense. The person standing at the shore is only holding one end of the seine, whilst other people are going by boat around a fish school. Hence, the shouting man in the boat rather wants to inform the man at the shore, that they [= the people in the boat] will go and pull the seine quickly, than to request him to do so.

Taking these two examples into account, one would have to conclude that the distinction of the forms -IAk and -IAgIŋ in the first person imperative in Dolgan is a pure number distinction. The form -IAk expresses first person imperative dual, the form -IAgIŋ expresses first person imperative plural. In most contexts, nevertheless, the forms do also express the opposition of minimal

vs. augmented inclusive due to the prototypical constellation of imperative speech situations.

3.3. Excursus: The dual-indicating item *bihikki*

The first person imperative is not the only domain in the grammar of Dolgan where number distinctions can be more fine-grained than singular vs. plural. There is an item *bihikki* ‘I together with another person’ (< *bihigi* ‘we’ + *ikki* ‘two’) which can indicate dual number⁵ in both inclusive and exclusive contexts:

- (9) *Kis-tari-n* *b̄ier-iek-te:ger* *en*
 daughter-POSS3PL-ACC give-PTCP.FUT-COMP **2SG**
bihikki-ni *ölör-ö* *kel-bit-tere.*
we.together-ACC kill-CVB.SIM come-PST2-3PL
 ‘They rather came to kill us [= you and me] than to give their daughter.’
 (PoKK_1964_TwoOrphanBoys_flk.036)
- (10) [...] *bihigi* *hit-a-bit* *di:n* **Oloksa: bihikki**, [...]
 1PL lie-PRS-1PL EMPH **Oloksa we.together**
 ‘[How long do they go by sledge,] we are lying though, Oloksa and I, [not going anywhere, what kind of sledge ride is that.]’
 (BeAM_199X_LegendOfSpiritOfTrees_nar.168)

What makes this item relevant for the study at hand, is the fact that it – though not obligatorily – can be combined with the first person imperative form -IAk, but not with the form -IAgIŋ. The following example shows an occurrence of *bihikki* together with the imperative form -IAk:

- (11) *Bi:r* *d'ie-ge* *d'ie-len-iek* *en*
 one house-DAT/LOC house-VBZ-IMP.1NSG 2SG
bihikki.
we.together
 ‘Let us [two] live together in one house.’
 (ErSV_1964_WarBirdsAnimals_flk.046)

Though this does not necessarily show that the imperative form -IAk expresses dual number, it shows that a dual interpretation of the form is available for speakers of Dolgan – otherwise the form could not be combined with the dual-indicating item *bihikki*.

⁵ Yakut (Sakha) exhibits also the item *ehikki* ‘you together with another person’ (< *ehigi* ‘you.PL’ + *ikki* ‘two’). For Dolgan, however, a corresponding form is neither mentioned in grammars nor present in the corpus.

4. Conclusion

This study started from the observation that Dolgan exhibits three forms in the first person imperative, although there are basically only two numbers, singular and plural. Hence, the question arose which functions these three forms fulfill. One of them – built with the suffix *-I:m* – unambiguously expresses first person singular imperative. The functions of the other two – built with the suffixes *-IAk* and *-IAgIŋ* – are more complex. The existing grammatical descriptions analyze them as expressing the opposition of exclusive vs. inclusive; this analysis could be falsified, as in both cases the addressee(s) is/are regularly included to the set of referents. Nevskaja (2005: 343) proposed that the forms would express the opposition minimal inclusive vs. augmented inclusive. This analysis holds true for most examples, but in a handful of examples it could be shown that also an exclusive reading is possible for both forms (examples (7) and (8)). Therefore, it can be concluded that the first person imperative forms *-IAk* and *-IAgIŋ* in Dolgan express rather a number distinction than a clusivity distinction. The paradigm of the imperative in Dolgan could, hence, be presented as follows:

	SG	DU	PL
1	-I:m	-IAk	-IAgIŋ
2	-Ø	-ŋ	
3	-DIn	-DInnAr	

Tab. 4: Personal endings in the imperative

Two details should finally be mentioned. First, it has to be emphasized that the number distinction dual vs. plural in most cases does not exclude the clusivity distinction minimal inclusive vs. augmented inclusive. But as there are also exclusive readings available for both of the forms, describing their distinction with a number opposition is more precise. Second, regarding the areal patterns – Samoyedic languages do exhibit a fully developed dual number – it stands to reason that this deviation from the standard Turkic pattern in Dolgan is contact-induced. Whether this may or may not be case, goes beyond the scope of this paper. In any case, not only the areal patterns should be regarded then, but also the exact functions of the corresponding forms in Yakut and Yakut dialects should be taken into account, as these may also give hints to the spread and origin of the phenomenon described here.

Abbreviations

1	first person	ACC	accusative
2	second person	ADV	adverb
3	third person	ALL	allative

COMP	comparative	INCL	inclusive
CONJ	conjunctive	LOC	locative
CVB.SEQ	sequential converb	MOD	modal particle
CVB.SIM	simultaneous converb	NSG	non-singular
DAT	dative	PL	plural
DU	dual	POSS	possessive suffix
EMPH	emphatic particle	PRS	present tense
EP	epenthetic vowel	PST2	second past tense
EXCL	exclusive	PTCP	participle
FRQ	frequentative	SG	singular
FUT	future tense	VBZ	verbalizer
IMP	imperative		

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Chris Lasse Däbritz

Universität Hamburg, Institut für Finnougristik/Uralistik, Überseering 35,
Postfach #29, 22297 Hamburg
E-Mail: chris.lasse.daebritz@uni-hamburg.de